

ANALYSIS OF CURRENT EFFORTS AND EXISTING PROBLEMS TO ENSURE WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN THE NORDIC COUNTRIES

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Abstract: Ensuring women's rights, creating equal opportunities and increasing their role in society are integral parts of democracy and human rights. Gender equality plays an important role in ensuring peace, harmony and the full realization of human potential through sustainable development. According to the International Index and Research, the countries with the highest level of gender equality in education, politics, economy and public life are Northern Europe. This article analyzes the specific models and strategies developed by these countries to protect women's rights and ensure gender equality, and highlights the existing problems.

Keywords: gender equality, women's rights, human rights, Nordic countries, gender policy, state strategy, feminism.

In today's globally developing world, we can observe the growing role and role of women in social, economic and political life. Gender equality, as integral concepts of public life, in fact, managed to be put on a par with the concepts of social justice, human rights and democracy. Klaus Schwab, founder and Executive Chairman of the World Economic Forum, said that more active participation of women in economic life is the key to a prosperous global economy. According to JIF research, the Global Gender Gap Index has improved by almost 10% compared to 2010 and 2020 [4][5]. This, in turn, testifies to the increasingly improved provision of women's rights in the fields of education, politics, and economics. Referring to the data of the Global Gender Gap Index, we see that the top 10 has not changed for 11 years [4]. These countries include 4 Nordic countries: Iceland, Norway, Finland and Sweden.

Table 1 The Global Gender Gap Index 2020

Rank	Country	Score	Rank change		Score change	
		0–1	2018	2018	2010	
1	Iceland	0.877	–	+0.018	+0	
2	Norway	0.842	–	+0.007	+0	
3	Finland	0.832	1	+0.012	+0	
4	Sweden	0.820	–1	–0.002	+0	
5	Nicaragua	0.804	–	–0.005	+0	
6	New Zealand	0.799	1	–0.002	+0	
7	Ireland	0.798	2	+0.002	+0	
8	Spain	0.795	21	+0.049	+0	
9	Rwanda	0.791	–3	–0.013	+0	
10	Germany	0.787	4	+0.011	+0	
11	Latvia	0.785	6	+0.027	+0	
12	Namibia	0.784	–2	–0.005	+0	

1.1.
Gender Gap Index 2020

Results of the Global

It is quite natural that these States have been at the forefront for 11 years, which is a notable event. Their acquisition of experience through research and analysis of gender policy strategies, their efforts to ensure women's rights along with human rights, will undoubtedly be useful for the development of Uzbekistan's gender policy at the present time.

Historically, under the influence of the processes that took place in the XVIII century in the European region, the concepts of human rights, equality and democracy are considered as fundamental values. Drawing attention directly to the problem of ensuring gender equality in the Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden), this model of development attracts attention by the fact that it has been widely recognized by the States of the world. The secret of the success of these states largely lies in the fact that they were able to raise gender equality to the level of state policy and form a public consciousness among the population regarding the theory of equality of men and women. The principle of equality is largely implemented through the creation of national mechanisms: the creation of a legislative framework on gender equality, the creation of special State institutions, the appointment of responsible persons on this issue, the request for plans and proposals from any State institutions to combat the problem of gender discrimination. I believe that the following 3 factors influenced the development of gender equality policy in Northern Europe:

1. That the women's feminist movement is developed in the region under consideration (the "feministiskt initiativ" party, in Norway - the "F!" movement, women's lobbying movements);

2. The presence of female representatives in the authorities of Northern Europe;

3. The orientation of state policy towards a socio-democratic orientation and the pursuit of common well-being, a sufficient legislative framework that ensures women's rights;

According to the World Economic Forum, a century of reforms is required to ensure gender equality in the world [4]. It follows from this that the existing problems in this direction still need a cardinal analysis. At the end of my article, I will review them and try to offer my practical solutions.

In Iceland, which has been leading in gender equality for eleven years, a unique model has been created, which is manifested in the fact that

gender equality in the country is 87% [4]. Women make up almost half of Iceland's population, and they were granted the right to vote in primary elections in 1915. Women have occupied their place in Government since the beginning of the XX century. And in 1980, for the first time in the whole world, it was in Iceland that a woman was elected head of state. According to the latest data, 88% of women in the Icelandic state have jobs, 65% of students studying in higher education institutions are women, and the country's parliament consists of 41% of women [10]. Worldwide, it is in Iceland that the share of women in the labor market is the highest, and in 2018 the law on the obligation of men and women to pay equal wages came into force [6]. As I mentioned earlier, Iceland also had and developed the 3 listed factors to ensure women's rights and gender equality. Article 23 of the Law on Equal Status and Equal Rights of Women and Men requires that gender equality issues be taught and promoted at all levels of education. In addition, since 2000, the Gender Equality Agency has been operating in the country, which monitors and balances progress in ensuring equality by revising the law "on Equal Status and Equal Rights of women and men". The Agency has a network of three parts, which includes the Council on the Status of Equality in the country, the complaints committee and the new center for Gender Equality [1]. These bodies jointly investigate, advertise, protect and verify laws on gender equality. Their goal is to create a legal, cultural, historical, social and psychological approach to gender equality. Nevertheless, Iceland recognizes that there are problems that have not yet been solved. One of them is a higher level of violence against women [1]. Here I will quote the words of the Prime Minister of Iceland Katrin Jakobsdottir, said on this occasion: "The statistics of violence between the sexes clearly show that there are many unresolved problems on the way to the complete elimination of gender differences. Violence against women is a cause and consequence of gender inequality. This is the priority of the state. Our goal is to achieve the goals set by the UN regarding gender equality in the fifth Sustainable Development Goal, and we hope to encourage other countries to do the same and step up our efforts to ensure the human rights of women and girls around the world."

In international rankings, Norway ranks first in terms of indicators such as gender equality and standard of living. The main goal of Norwegian efforts on women's rights and gender equality is to expand existing opportunities for women and girls, promote their right to self-determination and contribute to ensuring their rights and opportunities at the State level. About 70% of women in Norway are employed [6]. Gender equality has been one of the

reasons for Norway's tremendous economic growth and prosperity since the 1960s. In 1913, Norway was one of the first in the world to grant women full suffrage. Since the 70s of the XX century, the Norwegian mass media have begun active propaganda work to create a favorable public opinion to support women's equality and increase their representation in the government. The first such campaign began in 1967. As a result of this event, following the results of the first elections, the number of women in State bodies increased from 6 to 9.8%. In 1978, Norway passed the Gender Equality Act, prohibiting discrimination on the basis of sex in all spheres of public life. It is monitored by the Gender Equality Commission and the Office of the Commissioner for Gender Equality. Norway has joined the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women and reports annually to the UN on the situation of women in the country. The Government pays great attention to the reports of various public organizations on women's rights in the country and promptly responds to them. According to statistics, 36.3% of women of working age (from 20 to 66 years) hold senior positions at enterprises and enterprises [10]. In the Norwegian Parliament, women make up 41% of the Storting [10]. The Government's efforts to promote gender equality are based on the decisions and initiatives adopted at the World Women's Conference in Beijing in 1995 and the International Conference on Population and Development in Cairo in 1994, the UN Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, as well as the goals of universal rights and sustainable development, in particular, the fifth goal of gender equality and empowerment Norway not only conducts local work in this area, but also promotes women's rights in the international arena. In 2016-2020" the "action plan for gender equality in the field of women's rights and foreign policy", "The National Action Plan for Women, Peace and Security", combined with the international strategy for the elimination of harmful practices and relevant official documents, form the basis for Norway's international efforts to ensure gender equality. But in the country, nevertheless, the main problems are raging. First, the increase in violence against women. This situation has reached its peak, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. From this it can be concluded that the state of the global crisis has led to an increase in gender inequality. Secondly, in Norway there is a big difference in the wages of men and women. Officials also recognize that the state still has a century-long path to achieving pure gender equality.

The third and last State I want to consider is the Republic of Finland, which has its own model and position on equality in the world. I think the most popular word here would be “Taso-Arvo”, that is, "equality". Finland even has an official holiday - Equinox Day. It is celebrated on March 19 and coincides with the birthday of Finnish writer, journalist, playwright Minna Kant, who devoted her life to the struggle for women's rights. In the Finnish Government, 19 out of 10 ministers are women, and the proportion of women in Parliament is 46%. In Finland, the gender equality policy is coordinated by the Ministry of Social Affairs and Health and aims to increase gender equality through national gender equality action plans. The foundations of the gender equality policy derive from the Equality Law, State programs, as well as international treaties and legislation of the European Union. It can be said that the first steps towards equality between men and women were taken in Finland long before independence, that is, in the first half of the XIX century, when Finnish activists began fighting for the education of girls. The active women's movement and the activities of women's public organizations began to bear fruit: in 1906, a world-wide event took place in Finland: for the first time, women were granted full political rights. The Government's Action Plan on Gender Equality for 2020-2023 sets specific goals for ensuring gender equality and eliminating gender discrimination and establishes measures to implement the concept of equality in all administrative sectors [2].

Gender equality is aimed at the following areas and issues

- * working life, economics and decision-making in business
- * reconciliation of work and family and equal care
- * pre-school education and pre-school education
- * prevention of violence against pregnant women
- * sexual gender issues

Summing up, I can say that each of the 3 countries discussed above has its own policy and strategy. But the specifics common to them is that the Government has created a legal framework aimed at ensuring human and women's rights. The high level of social, political, and economic participation of women in Iceland, Norway, and Finland is determined by the activity of the women's movement here, and not by disregard for the country and their own destiny. Along with the fact that women's rights are an integral part of human rights, numerous practical efforts are being made in the minds of citizens from an early age. After all, in a state where equality, justice, and human rights are ensured, the development process is proceeding at an accelerated pace.

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